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A tactile model of Kunsthaus Graz

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Kunsthaus Graz is an exhibition and action venue, which is also known as ‘friendly alien’ due to its appearance. The creation of the current building and museum concept was preceded by several unrealized ideas, until the current museum was built as part of the European Capital of Culture 2003 and became one of Graz’s landmarks. It was planned by its architects Peter Cook and Colin Fournier in deliberate contrast to the surrounding baroque buildings. Following the architectural style of blobism, the shape of the building is designed organically and like an amoeba, punctuated by fifteen ‘nozzles’ that serve to let in light. This part of the Kunsthaus Graz is designed in blue and stands out from the other buildings in the complex, not least the listed Eiserne Haus, which was built between 1846 and 1848 as a modern department store. Kunsthaus Graz sees itself as an exhibition and action venue for contemporary art, new media, and photography. Due to the intended lack of permanent exhibitions and its own archive, it is characterized by a constant change of exhibitions. The museum is considered modern and forward-looking, the architecture unconventional and sometimes controversial (Kunsthaus Graz, 2025).

A tactile model of Kunsthaus Graz has been placed in front of the building. Created as part of the Graz Miniatures, a series of five tactile models displaying the city’s landmarks, it is primarily designed for visually impaired visitors. They navigate to the model using tactile ground surface indicators to then use it to better orient themselves in its surroundings and get an impression of Kunsthaus Graz. Visitors usually feel the surface of the model. Knowing that tactile models resemble the shape and arrangement of buildings and other objects, they assume that the same is the case with this model. Based on this assumption, the visually impaired visitor is able to construct a mental im-

age of the actual shape of the Kunsthaus Graz, including its round shape with the characteristic protruding ‘nozzles’ and the layout of the surrounding architectural complex. Visually non-impaired visitors perceive the same model very differently, not least because they are not necessarily familiar with tactile models. When viewing it visually, they recognize structural similarities between the visible parts of the model and the Kunsthaus Graz. This makes them assume that the shape of the model resembles that of the Kunsthaus Graz even in areas that remain hidden from the viewer’s position. Based on this assumption, the visually impaired visitor is able to construct a mental image of the shape of the Kunsthaus Graz.

The model features raised plaques that provide information about the name and function of the museum to those who know German Braille, typically visually impaired visitors. Corresponding plaques also mark the entrances to the Kunsthaus Graz, the streets adjacent to the building complex, and a nearby tram stop. These plaques indicate the locations of these features by being placed at their respective positions on the model. For visitors without visual impairments, however, this information remains mostly hidden. They are able to identify that information is available to those who know Braille, but they are not able to decode it themselves.

The tactile model employs two mechanisms to refer to Kunsthaus Graz, as has been outlined before: first, through the resemblance of its shape and the layout of the surrounding architectural complex; and secondly, through the use of German Braille to provide information about the name and function of the place as well as the positions of the entrances to the museum, neighbouring streets, and a nearby tram stop. The structural resemblance is of primary importance,

as is evidenced by the fact that the plaques would largely be rendered meaningless without the structural resemblance, whereas the structural resemblance would continue to function without the plaques. It should be noted that both mechanisms operate differently for visually impaired and non-impaired people.

Literature

Kunsthhaus Graz: *Kunsthhaus Graz*. 2025.

<https://www.museum-joanneum.at/kunsthhaus-graz>